

STATUS OF EUROPEAN ESTUARIES

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ABSTRACT

Studies of pollution status in particular estuaries provide information which may be useful generally in studies of other estuaries. Most estuarine pollution issues concern 1) point and nonpoint source contaminants, 2) eutrophication and hypoxia, 3) pathogen introduction and 4) urbanization and industrial development. Most of the estuarine pollution issues in the United States have been well known in Europe for decades. Assessment and monitoring of thermal discharges and of a variety of point and nonpoint source inorganic and organic chemical contaminants have been conducted in the Baltic Sea, Danish coast, French coast, German Bight, Netherlands coast, North Sea and Oslofjord.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the 1979 Statutory meetings of the International Council for the Exploration of the Seas (ICES) formal recommendations were made to the effect that member nations of ICES should prepare brief characterizations of important estuaries in North America and Europe. A basic concept in this was that interestuarine comparisons could be made which would provide generic and historical information useful to answer major questions in other estuaries. A result of the 1979 recommendation was the publication of ICES Cooperative Research Report No. 118, a compilation of several characterizations based on research results from northeast U.S. estuaries (1). The papers all stressed certain major problems or issues, i.e. trace metals or synthetic organics and their effects, or physical degradation of habitats.

More recently major governmental agencies have taken steps to determine what are the important contemporary issues or activities which seem to compromise estuarine habitat quality, particularly those affecting utilization of living marine resources as seafoods, but also those affecting other uses of estuaries and coastal waters. In a meeting held in May 1984, the U.S. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) sponsored a workshop (2) to identify and prioritize the principal questions and issues which mankind must address

if it is to manage successfully pollution abatement, habitat rehabilitation, and the use of estuaries in the production of seafoods. Of the four score of issues that were raised, a half dozen or so were deemed more important. These included 1) point and nonpoint source contamination of coastal marine waters by synthetic organic contaminants, such as PCBs; 2) releases of excessive amounts of nutrients to such waters and concomitant development of eutrophication and hypoxia; 3) introductions of pathogenic organisms (bacteria, viruses) and subsequent development of diseases in marine fishes and shellfishes; and 4) consequences of urbanization and industrial and harbor development, including the elimination of important habitats necessary to continued productivity of various forms of marine life. A more recent evaluation of issues by NOAA confirmed these priorities.

While the participants in the NOAA workshop had in mind the identification of issues unique to the United States, in fact these same issues are among the principal ones noted in European, Asian, African, and Latin American waterways and estuaries.

In preparing this paper several hundred ICES Marine Environmental Quality (MEQ) documents from 1975-1986 were reviewed, as were over 500 published papers, review articles, and books. It would be impossible in the time and pages allocated, to reference all the aforementioned titles. Therefore, I am using a number of case studies to provide insights into the status of European estuaries.

2. THE RESULTS OF THE REVIEW

In North America most attention has often been given to the consequences of catastrophic oil and chemical spills; the number of scientific papers and news releases on the Amoco Cadiz sinking and the release of toxic organics to the Rhine are ample testimony to this. Another way to characterize major European concerns and the status of estuaries is to examine papers given at national and international meetings. For instance, at the 14th European Marine Biology Symposium held in Germany in 1979 and titled "Protection of Life in the Sea", papers from Scotland (3) and England (4) noted a concern for the effects of pulp mill effluents discharged to sea lochs and tidal channels.

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Major effects on populations and species were measured.

In France the effects of thermal discharges to coastal waters from nuclear and steam electric power generating plants (5) are of concern. Several long-term studies of pollution in the southern North Sea have emphasized how contaminants from rivers and ocean disposal affect benthic communities (6) (7) and the prevalence of disease in finfish. The coastal waters of Holland have been heavily used during the past half century; managers and scientists from the Netherlands have therefore, instituted controls on the discharge of industrial and other wastes. To understand the consequences of pollution abatement, e.g. reductions in introductions of mercury wastes, Essink (8) is investigating the changes which occur with abatement.

Several European estuaries have been heavily contaminated with wastes for several decades. The Oslofjord is known to be polluted with a range of organic wastes having several sources. Gray (9) has proposed a long-term monitoring effort to assess subtle, chronic effects of organic wastes and document the effects from reducing contaminants. Similarly, Jones (10) developed a monitoring plan for use in the Orkney Islands in connection with the operation of an oil-handling facility.

As is often the case, North Sea embayments with reduced circulation or narrow mouths opening to the seas, e.g. the Baltic and Wadden Sea, frequently are characterized by reduced water quality. German and Scandinavian scientists began to monitor the German Bight and Baltic Sea for a variety of contaminants (11) (12) in the 1970's. Likewise, in the '60s scientists associated with the various Netherland sea research institutions (13) established benchmarks against which changes in pollution and its effects could be compared. By the late '70s and early '80s marine scientists began to document loadings to the Baltic Sea and other European coastal waters and to develop detailed assessments or characterizations of contaminants present. Bruneau (14) estimated the contaminant burden for the Baltic Sea from point and nonpoint sources from surrounding nations. He noted that while his estimates "may be too high, they are of proper magnitude." Better data collections and handling were recommended so as to optimize the reduction of pollution; Bruneau recommended concentrating on those abatement measures which are effective against the more serious pollutants. Using data available to ICES, Pawlak (15) also reported on the discharges and trends in discharges of organic matter and nutrients as well as heavy metals, organohalogen compounds, and petroleum hydrocarbons. While increased waste treatments have resulted in a 50% decrease in phosphorus input, increases in the inputs of nitrogen to rivers resulted in a 10% overall increase of nitrogen to the Baltic between 1969 and 1977. On the basis of these inputs, Leppakoski (16)

reported that human activities have caused "excessive eutrophication" and an accumulation of contaminants which are "seriously affecting the biomass of the Baltic." Subsequently, German workers in the southern North Sea have reported hypoxia off the Danish west coast and the north coast of the Federal Republic of Germany (17). Rosenberg (18), considering the several sources of nutrients leading to eutrophication and hypoxia, asks whether or not the situation is an immediate one throughout northern European seas, not just a potential problem? A contemporary paper by Larsson, (19) states that "...rough estimates indicate that man plays a dominant role in the eutrophication of the Baltic Sea." These authors note, however, that the various mechanisms involved are not fully known and therefore precise estimates cannot be made. They do point out that during the past decade the trend of increasing nutrient loadings and elevated BODs was broken through better treatment of sewage; but "...nitrogen inputs continue to increase because of the intensified use of fertilizers in agriculture."

The aforementioned overviews are concerned with larger, international seas. Throughout Europe local estuaries and embayments are being investigated and monitored. One representative estuary in the Ems-Dollard estuary in Holland. Since the 15th and 16th Centuries these waterways have been affected by land reclamation works, dike construction, and dredging and channelization. Moreover, since the 19th Century industrial effluents have been piped to the canals of northeast Netherlands. These canals had poor circulation and hence contaminants accumulated and had undesirable effects. A principal industrial contaminant was waste from potato flour manufacturing. It was decided to collect and discharge such wastes to the Wadden Sea and Ems-Dollard estuary. To determine the full effects of these and other wastes, an assessment and model were developed based on survey results from ecosystem research between 1973 and 1982. As seems true for many estuaries, the author of the study (20) noted that the effects of man "...cannot always be sharply distinguished from stress factors that are invariably already present in the estuary." However, for the issues studied, i.e. discharges of wastes, increased turbidity (from dredging), and increased nutrient concentrations (from runoff, synthetic detergents, and fertilizers), there are demonstrable effects, usually seen as measured change in primary production, increased hypoxia, and change in benthic community structure. In some instances these impact commercial fisheries, both spatially and temporally. All of these changes are similar to those seen in other European and North American estuaries, affected by anthropogenic activities. Also as with other coastal waters, full assessments are limited by a lack of historical or generic data.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Most of the pollution-related issues that have been identified for the United States have been noted in European estuaries. The biological consequences of these activities are also similar, as is the stated inability to deal fully with resulting problems because of lack of data. However, agencies responsible for management of coastal habitat quality have begun to organize existing data and develop models for use in management, at the same time as new research and monitoring studies are commissioned and funded.

4. LITERATURE CITED

- (1) Pearce, J. (ed). 1983. Review of Water Quality and Transport of Materials in Coastal and Estuarine Waters. International Council for the Exploration of the Seas. Cooperative Research Report No. 118. 216 pp.
- (2) NOAA. 1984. National Marine Pollution Research and Monitoring Issues. Preliminary Workshop Results, Easton, MD, 22-24 May 1984. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Rockville, MD.
- (3) Blackstock, J. 1979. A biochemical approach to assessment of organic effluent effects on the metabolism of the non-opportunistic polychaete *Glycera alba* (abstract). 14th European Marine Biology Symposium. Helgoland, F.R.G., 23-29 Sep. 1979. p. 10.
- (4) Millner, R. 1979. Pulp and paper-mill waste pollution in the Swale, a tidal channel (abstract). 14th European Marine Biology Symposium. Helgoland, F.R.G., 23-29 Sep. 1979. p. 64.
- (5) Castel, J. 1979. Response of estuarine zooplankters to thermal discharge from a power plant (abstract). 14th European Marine Biological Symposium. Helgoland, F.R.G., 23-29 Sep. 1979. pp. 18-19.
- (6) DeConinck, L., J. Govaere, C. Heip, and D. VanDamme. 1979. Stability of benthic communities and the assessment of water pollution in the Southern Bight of the North Sea (abstract). 14th European Marine Biological Symposium. Helgoland, F.R.G., 23-29 Sep. 1979. p. 28.
- (7) Rachor, E. 1979. The inner German Bight-an ecologically sensitive area as indicated by the bottom fauna (abstract). 14th European Marine Biology Symposium. Helgoland, F.R.G., 23-29 Sep. 1979. p. 83.
- (8) Essink, K. 1979. Mercury pollution in the Ems Estuary (abstract). 14th European Marine Biology Symposium. Helgoland, F.R.G., 23-29 Sep. 1979. p. 33.
- (9) Gray, J. 1979. Devising a monitoring programme for assessing chronic effects of pollution: an example from Oslofjord, Norway (abstract). 14th European Marine Biology Symposium. Helgoland, F.R.G., 23-29 Sep. 1979. p. 38.
- (10) Jones, A. 1979. The design and development of monitoring programme for Scapa Flow, Orkney, U.K. (abstract). 14th European Marine Biology Symposium. Heloland, F.R.G., 23-29 Sep. 1979. p. 46.
- (11) Schmidt, D. and A. Neubauer-Ziebarth. 1979. Comparison of trace heavy metal levels from monitoring in the German Bight and the southwestern Baltic Sea (abstract) 14th European Marine Biology Symposium. Helgoland, F.R.G., 23-29 Sep. 1979. p. 89.
- (12) Von Wachenfeldt, T. 1979. Eutrophication and trace elements in the Oresund area (abstract). 14th European Marine Biology Symposium. Helgoland, F.R.G., 23-29 Sep. 1979. p. 102.
- (13) Wolff, W., and J. Zijlstra. 1979. Management of areas: example Wadden Sea. (abstract). 14th European Marine Biology Symposium. Helgoland, F.R.G., 23-29 Sep. 1979. p. 103.
- (14) Bruneau, L. 1980. Pollution from industries in the drainage area of the Baltic. *Ambio*, 9(3-4):145-152.
- (15) Pawlak, J. 1980. Land-based inputs of some major pollutants to the Baltic Sea. *Ambio*, 9(3-4):163-167.
- (16) Leppakoski, E. 1980. Man's impact on the Baltic ecosystem. *Ambio*, 9(3-4):174-181.
- (17) Dethlefsen, V. and von Westernhagen. 1983. Oxygen deficiency and effects on bottom fauna in the eastern German Bight, 1982. *Meeresforsch.* 60:42-53.
- (18) Rosenberg, R. 1985. Eutrophication - the future marine coastal nuisance? *Mar. Poll. Bull.*, 16(6):227-231.
- (19) Larsson, U., R. Elmgren, and F. Wulff. 1985. Eutrophication and the Baltic Sea: causes and consequences. *Ambio*, 14(1):9-14.
- (20) Rijkswaterstaat. 1985. Biological Research. Ems-Dollard Estuary. Rijkswaterstaat Communications. The Hague. No. 40. 182 pp.